

Nuclear Data Adjustment Guided by the Coverage Quantification Metric q_c

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ABSTRACT

Nominal values and uncertainties in nuclear data are key factors in reactor physics simulation and criticality safety analyses. We present a Bayesian data assimilation framework that uses an information-theoretic metric, q_c , to quantify the collective experimental coverage on a target nuclear data application and guide its adjustment by using the benchmarks from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project. Candidate benchmark experiments are ranked by their contributions to q_c , and a generalized linear least squares method is then applied to assimilate the benchmarks' eigenvalue information and update the application's posterior distribution. This framework prioritizes experiment selections by maximizing uncertainty coverage for each application response (i.e., cross section at a given energy). We demonstrate this approach for the ²³⁹Pu fission cross sections under a 56-energy-group structure updated with a fixed pool of candidate benchmarks. Across five sets of experiments that start with different initial experiment selections, the q_c rises rapidly and then saturates. This saturation coincides with the stabilization of the inferred bias, which indicates a consistent convergence of the posterior adjustment. Compared with a conventional similarity index, c_k , the q_c -guided sets yield higher equivalent experimental relevance by aggregating complementary information from multiple experiments and explicitly accounting for measurement uncertainty. The study offers a systematic base for experiment prioritization in posterior updates and demonstrates a robust performance of our proposed q_c metric for nuclear data nominal value adjustment and uncertainty reduction.

Keywords: nuclear data adjustment; ²³⁹Pu cross sections; Bayesian data assimilation; experimental coverage; similarity analysis; nuclear criticality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reliable reactor physics predictions and criticality safety analyses rely heavily on the quality of evaluated nuclear data and their associated covariances. Uncertainties in microscopic nuclear data propagate through transport and depletion calculations and appear as uncertainties in key integral responses such as multiplication factor k_{eff} , reactivity coefficients and power distributions, and their best estimates from simulators rely on the accuracy of the nuclear data nominals. Over time, nuclear data libraries have advanced substantially in both their content and quantified uncertainty. The US ENDF/B-VIII.1 release introduced significant reevaluations of major actinides and structural materials, extended sub libraries, and improved covariance coverage to better align with applications across fission, fusion, and shielding problems [1]. In parallel, the JEFF (Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion)

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project released JEFF-4.0 in 2025 with upgraded major actinides, fission yields, and fission-product data [2]. Released in 2021, the fifth version of the Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library (JENDL-5) integrated numerous special-purpose files for reactor utilizations [3]. Together, these efforts demonstrate a consistent community practice: new measurements, covariance improvements, and application-driven validation justify library updates when they demonstrably reduce biases and uncertainties or resolve inconsistencies with integral benchmarks.

A foundation in the application-driven evolution is the systematic use of high-quality integral benchmarks—especially those from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) and the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation (IRPhE) Project—to test and validate application-relevant regimes [4]. In practice, limitations in available nuclear data covariances and inconsistencies among evaluated cross sections can reduce confidence in calculated responses and might obscure physical insight via compensating effects. These well-recognized issues motivate principled adjustment methodologies that use integral data to reduce uncertainty and correct biased nuclear data in a traceable way [5]. Bayesian data assimilation (DA) provides the statistical framework to do so.

Under linear and Gaussian assumptions, DA reduces to the generalized linear least squares (GLLS) formulation and has already been implemented in the SCALE/TSURFER module [6], which jointly leverages current benchmark sensitivities and eigenvalue measurements to update the means and covariances of nuclear data so that code predictions for the target benchmark better align with measurement. Complementary stochastic approaches (e.g., MOCABA) relax intrusive requirements and offer alternative routes to assimilate integral data [7].

With these DA methods, experiment selection for nuclear data adjustment has typically been instructed by expertise or the similarity index c_k , which quantifies the alignment between the sensitivity vectors of an experiment and the application under prior nuclear data covariance weighting. Although effective and computationally efficient, c_k is inherently pairwise and linear and does not account for redundancy across multiple experiments or the measurement uncertainty level, both of which are important when prioritizing experiments in assimilation [8].

To address this gap, our recent work introduced an information-theoretic metric, q_c , to quantify the experimental coverage and evaluate the collective value of multiple benchmarks in reducing the prior uncertainty of the target quantity of interest (QoI) (i.e., application response). In a previous study, we used simulated k_{eff} responses from criticality benchmarks as predictors (i.e., experiments) to adjust the covariance of each groupwise cross section, denoted as an “application.” Under linear and Gaussian assumptions, q_c provides a transparent interpretation in terms of posterior/prior uncertainty reduction and can be related to an “equivalent” c_k similarity level. Importantly, it highlights redundancy and utilizes multiple experiments with different c_k levels to increase experimental relevance [9].

In the present work, we advance that concept one step further. Rather than focusing only on covariance adjustment, we target adjustment of the nuclear data nominal values by using q_c and the same benchmark dataset to guide experiment selection and assimilation. Specifically, we investigate this practice with cross sections of ^{239}Pu fission, which is a significant reaction for criticality safety and advanced fuel cycles. We integrate q_c with the DA pipeline to (i) use q_c to rank candidate benchmarks by their ability to reduce uncertainty in the target cross section and (ii) assimilate the selected experiments by using GLLS to update the means and uncertainties. This work shows how q_c -guided experiment selection can effectively inform nuclear data adjustments while quantifying their uncertainty reduction potential.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 shows the methodology of the q_c metric and its connection to the similarity index and uncertainty reduction. Section 3 describes the benchmark experiment data, numerical test, and results for ^{239}Pu fission cross section adjustments. Section 4 summarizes our conclusions and describes potential future work.

2. METHODOLOGY

The q_c metric is based on mutual information between a set of predictor variables and a target QoI and provides a systematic way to judge how informative the predictors are for the QoI. Within our work,

the QoI and predictors are denoted as “application” and “experiment” responses, respectively, and the experiments have corresponding measurements. High-fidelity simulations provide calculations for both application and experiment. Once experiment responses are measured, we can update the application response with Bayesian DA. This requires generating a cloud of randomized samples that respects the physics between experiment and application responses. A high-fidelity simulator is used to build this cloud with uncertainties relevant to the modeling error. The more uncertainties involved, the more inflated the cloud would be, and the lower the q_c between experiments and the target application. This causes degradation when using experiments to infer the uncertainty of the application response.

2.1. Coverage quantification metric q_c

The information-theoretic coverage quantification metric q_c can serve as an index to evaluate experiment relevance. It evaluates the normalized mutual information between an application response, Y_a , and a set of predictor responses (i.e., experiments, Y_e). This q_c metric is defined in Eq. (1) with mutual information, which is defined between two or more variables as the reduction in entropy (i.e., $H(Y_a)$ reduction upon knowledge of Y_e and the measurements). Here, I is the mutual information between Y_a and Y_e , given μ (i.e., information about the underlying parameters, reference values, parameter uncertainties, measurements, measurement uncertainties).

$$q_c(Y_e, Y_a) = 1 - e^{-I(Y_a; Y_e, \mu)} = 1 - e^{-[H(Y_a) - H(Y_a|Y_e, \mu)]} \quad (1)$$

This definition decouples experiment relevance from the specific DA algorithm and remains valid for nonlinear models and non-Gaussian priors. As our previous work shows [10], in the linear and Gaussian constraints, this q_c metric can be interpreted as how much of the application’s first-order sensitivity can be represented by the given experiment’s sensitivity subspace (Figure 1). We previously demonstrated that, under the linear/Gaussian assumptions, q_c can be simplified to a unitless measure of the uncertainty reduction of the target application after conditioning on selected experiments, as Eq. (2) shows. Notably, σ_a^{prior} and σ_a^{post} are the application response’s prior standard deviation and posterior standard deviation, respectively.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of experimental coverage of an application under linear assumption.

$$q_c(Y_e, Y_a) = 1 - \frac{\sigma_a^{post}}{\sigma_a^{prior}} \quad (2)$$

2.2. Posterior application with Bayesian updating

This work focuses on demonstrating how q_c provides a measure of experimental coverage and guides the experiment inclusions for Bayesian updating on the application response. Under linear and Gaussian assumptions in this work, we apply GLLS to obtain the application posterior bias, ΔY_a^{post} , and uncertainty, Σ_a^{post} , which employ first-order sensitivities with prior covariance weighting, as shown in

Eqs. (3) and (4). Prior efforts by Huang [11] and Hoefer [7] show that the stochastic GLLS update of bias and uncertainty is equivalent to the deterministic formulation based on first-order sensitivities and the covariance matrix. The stochastic form is also given in Eqs. (3) and (4). In those two equations, S_a and S_e are sensitivity profiles for application and experiment, respectively. $\Sigma_{\sigma\sigma}$ is the covariance for their common source of uncertainties, Σ_m is centered by respective reference values, and N is the number of stochastic samples. Thus, by means of GLLS updating, the proposed q_c metric in Eq. (2) can be further expressed in terms of the sensitivities and the provided covariance information, as shown in Eq. (5).

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta Y_a^{post} &= -S_a^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_e \left(S_e^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_e + \Sigma_m \right)^{-1} \Delta Y_e \\ &= -\frac{1}{N} (Y_a^{prior})^T Y_e^{prior} \left(\frac{1}{N} Y_e^{prior T} Y_e^{prior} + \Sigma_e^m \right)^{-1} \Delta Y_e\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_a^{post} &= S_a^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_a - S_a^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_e \left(S_e^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_e + \Sigma_m \right)^{-1} S_e^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_a \\ &= \frac{1}{N} Y_a^{prior T} Y_a^{prior} - \frac{1}{N^2} (Y_a^{prior})^T Y_e^{prior} \left(\frac{1}{N} Y_e^{prior T} Y_e^{prior} + \Sigma_e^m \right)^{-1} (Y_e^{prior})^T Y_a^{prior}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

$$q_c(Y_e, Y_a) = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{S_a^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} (I - S_e (S_e^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_e + \Sigma_m)^{-1} S_e^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma}) S_a}{S_a^T \Sigma_{\sigma\sigma} S_a}}\quad (5)$$

For linear and Gaussian data, ML methods (e.g., neural networks) would reproduce the same q_c result as GLLS. When nonlinear or non-Gaussian effects are significant, ML is needed to evaluate mutual information based on data samples. In future work, we will demonstrate q_c in that implementation, in which linear methods are expected to perform poorly.

2.3. Similarity index c_k

The covariance-weighted, sensitivity-based c_k similarity index has been applied by the nuclear criticality community to provide a linear relevance metric, as defined in Eq. (6). Compared with q_c , c_k shows pairwise similarity between a single experiment and the target application and does not capture multi-experiment coverage nor does it consider the measurement uncertainty level of experiments. In our previous work [10], we showed how q_c can be interpreted as a similarity index similar to c_k , and we use an equivalent index $c_{k,equiv}$ derived from Eq. (7) in this work to show that q_c -guided selections would provide higher relevance by aggregating multiple experiments.

$$c_k = \frac{s_a^T C_{\sigma\sigma} s_{e,i}}{\sqrt{s_a^T C_{\sigma\sigma} s_a} \sqrt{s_{e,i}^T C_{\sigma\sigma} s_{e,i}}}\quad (6)$$

$$c_{k,equiv} = \sqrt{1 - (1 - q_c)^2}\quad (7)$$

2.4. Adjustment under experiment prioritization indicated by q_c

To implement q_c , we rank a set of experiments for a given application as follows:

- (i) Given the pool of candidate benchmark experiments, decide on a high- c_k experiment as an initial selection.
- (ii) Given the first experiment selection, obtain the second experiment that maximizes q_c between the two selected experiments and the target application (i.e., maximizing this collective q_c).
- (iii) Iteratively add the experiment that yields the largest collective q_c when combined with the already-selected set.
- (iv) Continue until q_c saturates or the pool of experiments is exhausted.
- (v) Update posterior means and uncertainties with inclusion of each selected experiment according to the q_c metric.

3. NUMERICAL TEST AND RESULTS

To show the performance of the proposed q_c metric, we use eigenvalue k_{eff} as the predictor variable (i.e., experiment response) and treat the 56-group ^{239}Pu fission cross sections as the application response. In this paper, we provide a few thermal energy groups as application result examples. The study employs 425 criticality benchmarks from 79 evaluations in the *ICSBEP Handbook*, spanning highly enriched uranium (HEU), intermediate enriched uranium (IEU), low enriched uranium (LEU), Pu, and mixed U/Pu contents in metal, solution, and composite array forms. The benchmark evaluations are summarized in Table I. The numbers inside the parentheses indicate how many benchmarks were used from that evaluation. The numbers inside the brackets indicate the experiment indices for the corresponding evaluation. These serve as simpler notations when demonstrating the q_c -guided experiment ordering. Their sensitivity profiles and k_{eff} prior distribution from nuclear data are calculated from SCALE/Tsunami with the ENDF VII.1 56-group library. As for the ^{239}Pu fission cross section applications, their nominals and prior uncertainties were obtained from the SCALE 56-group covariance library.

Table I. Summary of Benchmark Evaluations Applied

HEU-MET-FAST-005 (6) [1-6]	HEU-MET-FAST-038 (2) [33-34]	IEU-MET-FAST-002 (1) [103]	LEU-COMP-THERM-080 (11) [244-254]	PU-MET-FAST-008 (1) [339]
HEU-MET-FAST-008 (1) [7]	HEU-MET-FAST-040 (1) [35]	IEU-MET-FAST-003 (2) [104-105]	LEU-SOL-THERM-002 (3) [255-257]	PU-MET-FAST-010 (1) [340]
HEU-MET-FAST-009 (2) [8-9]	HEU-MET-FAST-052 (1) [36]	IEU-MET-FAST-004 (2) [106-107]	LEU-SOL-THERM-003 (9) [258-266]	PU-MET-FAST-018 (1) [341]
HEU-MET-FAST-010 (2) [10-11]	HEU-MET-FAST-065 (1) [37]	IEU-MET-FAST-005 (2) [108-109]	LEU-SOL-THERM-004 (7) [267-273]	PU-MET-FAST-022 (1) [342]
HEU-MET-FAST-011 (1) [12]	HEU-MET-FAST-080 (1) [38]	IEU-MET-FAST-006 (1) [110]	MIX-COMP-FAST-005 (1) [274]	PU-MET-FAST-023 (1) [343]
HEU-MET-FAST-013 (1) [13]	HEU-MET-FAST-086 (5) [39-43]	IEU-MET-FAST-008 (1) [111]	MIX-COMP-FAST-006 (1) [275]	PU-MET-FAST-024 (1) [344]
HEU-MET-FAST-015 (1) [14]	HEU-MET-FAST-092 (4) [44-47]	IEU-MET-FAST-009 (1) [112]	MIX-COMP-THERM-001 (4) [276-279]	PU-SOL-THERM-001 (6) [345-350]
HEU-MET-FAST-016 (2) [15-16]	HEU-MET-FAST-093 (1) [48]	IEU-MET-FAST-019 (2) [113-114]	MIX-COMP-THERM-002 (6) [280-285]	PU-SOL-THERM-002 (7) [351-357]
HEU-MET-FAST-017 (1) [17]	HEU-MET-FAST-094 (2) [49-50]	LEU-COMP-THERM-001 (8) [115-122]	MIX-COMP-THERM-004 (11) [286-296]	PU-SOL-THERM-003 (8) [358-365]
HEU-MET-FAST-018 (2) [18-19]	HEU-SOL-THERM-001 (10) [51-60]	LEU-COMP-THERM-002 (5) [123-127]	MIX-COMP-THERM-008 (28) [297-324]	PU-SOL-THERM-004 (13) [366-378]
HEU-MET-FAST-019 (2) [20-21]	HEU-SOL-THERM-013 (3) [61-64]	LEU-COMP-THERM-008 (17) [128-144]	MIX-SOL-THERM-002 (3) [325-327]	PU-SOL-THERM-005 (9) [379-387]
HEU-MET-FAST-020 (2) [22-23]	HEU-SOL-THERM-014 (3) [65-67]	LEU-COMP-THERM-010 (30) [145-174]	MIX-SOL-THERM-007 (7) [328-334]	PU-SOL-THERM-006 (3) [388-390]
HEU-MET-FAST-021 (2) [24-25]	HEU-SOL-THERM-016 (3) [68-70]	LEU-COMP-THERM-017 (29) [175-203]	PU-MET-FAST-001 (1) [335]	PU-SOL-THERM-007 (8) [391-398]
HEU-MET-FAST-024 (1) [26]	HEU-SOL-THERM-028 (18) [71-88]	LEU-COMP-THERM-042 (7) [204-210]	PU-MET-FAST-002 (1) [336]	PU-SOL-THERM-011 (12) [399-410]
HEU-MET-FAST-025 (5) [27-31]	HEU-SOL-THERM-029 (7) [89-95]	LEU-COMP-THERM-050 (18) [211-228]	PU-MET-FAST-005 (1) [337]	PU-SOL-THERM-020 (15) [411-425]
HEU-MET-FAST-030 (1) [32]	HEU-SOL-THERM-030 (7) [96-102]	LEU-COMP-THERM-078 (15) [229-243]	PU-MET-FAST-006 (1) [338]	

Given a fixed experiment pool, we conduct a test to check (i) if q_c is correctly evaluating coverage by uncertainty reduction, (ii) if q_c saturation coincides with the convergence of posterior updates, (iii) if a

posterior cross section under a saturated q_c falls within its prior uncertainty, and (iv) if the same saturated q_c given different experiment sets yields consistent cross section adjustment. These four aspects evaluate the robustness and correctness of nuclear data adjustment when maximizing the experimental coverage (i.e., when saturating q_c). Per application, detailed steps are as follows:

- (i) For a certain application, find the five experiments with the top-five highest c_k .
- (ii) Starting with a q_c -driven experiment selection, with each high- c_k as the initial selection, follow the procedures described in Section 2.4.

By forcing a different initial experiment as a selection starting point for a given cross section application, we see different experiment orderings until q_c convergence. Those q_c -guided orderings are determined based on the initial selection—thus, five different sets of experiment selections are made for posterior calculations.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 for two applications: ^{239}Pu σ_f under energies 0.1eV and 0.0253eV, respectively. In the two figures, the upper subplot shows how q_c accumulates when adding experiments one by one. The first 15 q_c -prioritized experiment selections are provided in Table II and Table III per application (refer to Table I for the benchmark names of those experiment indices). The lower subplot shows how the posterior mean for this cross section is correspondingly updated with the q_c -selected experiments, and the prior distribution (black line) and final q_c -converged posterior distributions are plotted with error bars. We plot the q_c and posterior evolutions for the five sets with different colored curves. From the two applications demonstrated, the five q_c converging curves are consistent per application, and the collective q_c increases rapidly as the highest-ranked experiments are incorporated, whereas the posterior cross section oscillates with a certain amount of experiment inclusions before q_c converges. Both q_c and posterior cross sections exhibit clear saturation after around 100 experiments are added.

Figure 2. Plutonium-239 $\sigma_f(E=0.1 \text{ eV})$: collective q_c (upper subplot) and posterior updating (lower subplot).

Table II. The q_c -guided First-15 Experiment Selections for Application of ^{239}Pu $\sigma_f(E=0.1 \text{ eV})$

Ordering	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10th	11th	12th	13th	14th	15th
SET-1	326	60	51	327	282	333	272	127	151	284	53	301	102	126	273
SET-2	325	60	51	391	284	327	333	282	126	137	272	53	102	151	326
SET-3	324	60	51	327	282	333	284	126	137	272	53	102	151	326	301
SET-4	284	326	60	391	51	327	333	272	127	151	282	53	301	102	126
SET-5	282	326	60	327	51	333	272	127	151	284	53	301	102	126	273

Notably, the experiments prioritized by q_c vary by test because of the different initial selection, as shown in Table II and Table III. As explained in Figure 1, under the linear assumption, we maximize q_c to find the experimental subspace that explains most of the application uncertainty. After a high- c_k experiment is selected, the algorithm seeks for an experiment that minimizes the non-coverage part. Therefore, another high- c_k experiment is not necessarily the next selection. A medium- c_k or even low- c_k experiment can be prioritized if it provides non-coverage information. Thus, once the first selection differs, the consequential experiment would be distinctive even if it is given the same experiment pool.

For each experiment selection set per application, converged posteriors are achieved at the same time when q_c saturates, and additional experiments contribute progressively trivial changes in q_c and posteriors. This indicates that the experiment ranking induced by q_c identifies experiments that are both collectively informative and non-redundant for cross section adjustment. When comparing results of the five sets per application, although the oscillation of the posterior updating curve varies at the beginning because of distinctive initial selections, consistent posterior convergences are identified given different q_c -prioritized experiments. At around 100 experiments added, the attainable q_c is also consistent per set, and the posterior cross section updated under the saturated q_c is within the prior distribution and justifies this cross section adjustment.

Figure 3. Plutonium-239 $\sigma_f(E=0.0253 \text{ eV})$: collective q_c (upper subplot) and posterior updating (lower subplot).

Table III. The q_c -guided First-15 Experiment Selections for Application of ^{239}Pu $\sigma_f(E=0.0253 \text{ eV})$

Ordering	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10th	11th	12th	13th	14th	15th
SET-1	326	60	327	51	127	272	301	318	333	102	325	53	139	300	126
SET-2	325	60	390	51	327	127	272	301	318	326	333	103	53	139	300
SET-3	324	60	390	51	327	127	272	301	318	326	333	103	53	139	300
SET-4	284	326	60	327	51	301	134	272	318	333	325	103	139	53	300
SET-5	301	326	390	282	60	51	327	134	272	102	137	53	325	333	285

We see that q_c saturates to 0.5 in Application: fission-EG49 | 0.1 eV

Figure 2 and to 0.6 in Figure 3, which means 50% and 60% uncertainty reductions in cross section, respectively. The reduction level indicated by q_c matches what we see in the error bars in the lower subplots. Both application updates indicate that the posterior cross section should be higher than the prior ones. In the legend of the upper subplots of each application, we list the five highest c_k values. Within the figure labels, we print the equivalent c_k values calculated by Eq. (7). Compared with the

maximum c_k as 0.742 and 0.751. the $c_{k, equiv}$ values are 0.867 and 0.917 in Application: fission-EG49 | 0.1 eV

Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. This is much higher than a pairwise similarity level and indicates that aggregating more experiments rather than only the high- c_k experiments can yield more experimental relevance and coverage on an application. In this work, we verified that q_c consistently prioritizes the non-redundant experimental information and yields reasonable, adjusted cross sections within its prior distribution when q_c converges. We confirm that q_c growth and posterior stabilization converge to the same level at the same time. This work demonstrates that q_c provides a robust and interpretable path to effectively adjusting nuclear data and reducing its posterior uncertainty.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work describes a framework for using the q_c metric to adjust nuclear data nominal values and uncertainties by assimilating calculated and measured eigenvalue information of available criticality benchmark experiments. The q_c information-theoretic metric quantifies the collective experimental relevance of multiple benchmarks for a target cross section application. Under linear and Gaussian assumptions, q_c has an intuitive interpretation as a prior-to-posterior uncertainty reduction ratio. Using groupwise ^{239}Pu fission cross sections as applications, we demonstrated the performance of q_c -guided nuclear data adjustment with 425 ICSBEP criticality benchmarks as candidate experiments. Per application, the test that uses five distinct high- c_k experiments as initial selections showed that saturated q_c correlates with the stabilized application posterior distributions when progressively adding experiments. This provides evidence that q_c has a robust and interpretable basis for experiment prioritization and nuclear data adjustment. Accumulating the q_c -selected experiments can achieve higher experimental relevance than using only the highest- c_k experiment from the current benchmark pool. Practically, this q_c metric offers a quantitative method to effectively select the most informative experiments and to diagnose experimental redundancy among high- c_k experiments. Future work will demonstrate more results and show how the q_c framework benefits current nuclear data adjustment methods. We will also focus on applying this q_c metric and methodology to nonlinear and non-Gaussian problems and embedding q_c into multi-objective optimization for new experiment designs.

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